

Adding seismic picks from Ocean Bottom Seismometers (OBS) into the ISC Bulletin: the example of the “7D Cascadia Initiative Experiment, OBS Component”

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Introduction

The International Seismological Centre (ISC) is a non-profit organization with the mandate of providing the definitive and most comprehensive record of Earth's seismicity, the ISC Bulletin (www.isc.ac.uk/iscbulletin/). Thanks to a unique cooperation within the seismological community, the ISC is able to collect, integrate and re-process parametric instrumental seismic data from ~130 seismological agencies around the world (www.isc.ac.uk/iscbulletin/agencies). Various types of instrumental parametric data are collected at the ISC: from basic focus parameters (location) to moment tensor solutions and various types of seismic station data, primarily phase arrival times and associated amplitudes-periods. Whilst the main contributors to the ISC are monitoring agencies operating at various scales, the ISC Bulletin can benefit from additional parametric data coming from temporary deployments. With exception to a few JMA (Japanese Meteorological Agency, www.isc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/agency-get?agency=JMA) stations, no monitoring agency is routinely picking seismic phase arrival times from Ocean Bottom Seismometers (OBS). The lack of seismic station data outside continental areas makes OBS picks even more valuable to users of the ISC datasets (www.isc.ac.uk). In this contribution we show how manual picks of body-waves from the OBS data of the Cascadia Initiative Community Experiment (http://www.fdsn.org/networks/detail/7D_2011/, IRIS OBSIP, 2011) were integrated into the ISC Bulletin and used for the ISC hypocentre relocation. The picks have been done under the supervision of ISC seismologists by the second author of this report during July-August 2016 as part of his summer internship. In total, approximately 6400 picks of primary and secondary wave arrivals have been picked for large earthquakes at teleseismic distances and moderate-to-large earthquakes in the local/regional distance range. Despite the high noise level of OBS waveforms, over 50% of the picks have contributed to ISC relocations.

Finally, we encourage researchers processing data from temporary deployments to send parametric data to the ISC in order to improve the overall configuration of the network of stations reporting to the ISC; this in turn will improve specialised ISC datasets (e.g., ISC-EHB, GT and ISC-GEM) and offer an even denser dataset to ISC users.

The 7D Cascadia Initiative Community Experiment: the OBS component

The aim of the Experiment (running from 2011) is to complement the onshore seismic and geodetic network of the Pacific Northwest with an array of seismometers deployed on the seafloor to study various processes taking place between the Gorda and Juan de Fuca plates. Here we are interested in the OBS component of the experiment and we use the seismic waveforms freely available via the

IRIS website (<http://ds.iris.edu/mda/7D?timewindow=2011-2017>). Waveforms from the experiment are available from 18:12:00 on 25th July 2011 to 10:52:18 on 10th October 2015. Figure 1 shows the OBS locations as of July 2016 (over 250 stations deployed at different times). An interactive map with more information on each OBS station is available at the IRIS website (<http://ds.iris.edu/gmap/7D?timewindow=2011-2017>).

Figure 1: location map of the OBS stations color-coded by depth below sea level.

It has to be noted that the Pacific Northwest is a well monitored area with plenty of onshore stations. This is shown in Figure 2 where, for the same area of Figure 1, the seismic stations registered in the International Registry of Seismic Stations (IR, www.isc.ac.uk/registries) and having at least one body-wave arrival time in the ISC Bulletin between 2011-07-25 and 2015-10-10 are plotted. The 7D-OBS Experiment is clearly a substantial (temporary) extension of the continental network and we aimed at adding as many meaningful picks as possible during the two months of our co-author's internship at the ISC.

Figure 2: location map of the IR stations reporting phase data to the ISC between 2011-07-25 and 2015-10-10 in the same area shown in Figure 1.

Earthquakes selected and waveforms downloaded

Compared to continental stations, the OBS time series should show a higher noise level and the picking should be, in general, more prone to errors. Therefore, to start with more “readable” time series, we downloaded waveforms for major-great global earthquakes (i.e., moment magnitude $M_w \geq 7.0$) that have occurred since the beginning of the 7D-OBS experiment (25th July 2011) up to the last reviewed month in the ISC Bulletin (www.isc.ac.uk/iscbulletin/review/) when this work started in July 2016 (meaning earthquake data up to July 2013). After gaining experience with the dataset of large global earthquakes we also added events of lower magnitude (down to $M_w 5.0$) that occurred at local-regional distances from the 7D-OBS experiment between August 2013 and October 2015.

Figure 3 shows the distribution of the 99 earthquakes studied in this contribution; it is possible to observe the large global earthquakes at large teleseismic distances from the 7D-OBS network, and the smaller events within $\sim 30^\circ$ of the 7D-OBS network. Table A1 in the Appendix lists the earthquakes picked in this work.

Figure 3: map showing the location of the earthquakes selected for picking (99 in total) plotted according to the Agnew (2014) star symbols and colour-coded by depth. The dashed contours are calculated considering a central station of the 7D-OBS network (black triangles) and are shown for reference. The majority of large earthquakes are outside the local-regional distance range. The moment magnitude M_w is that determined by the GCMT project, <http://www.globalcmt.org/>, see also Dziewonski et al. (1981) and Ekström et al. (2012).

Figure 4 is a summary of the waveforms (BHZ channels only) obtained via the IRIS *breq_fast* waveform request (https://ds.iris.edu/ds/nodes/dmc/manuals/breq_fast/). For most of the earthquakes selected the number of stations available (NSTA) is around 35. For one event NSTA is more than 40 but for a few events NSTA is below 5. Considering the waveforms available for each individual event, it is possible to notice from Figure 4 that the OBS stations were quite close to each other as the epicentral distance range for the same event is small (i.e., the inter-station distances between OBS stations operating at a certain time was at most a few hundred km). In total we obtained 3183 waveforms and attempted to pick each of them during July-August 2016.

Figure 4: timeline of the earthquakes selected and epicentral distance of the waveforms downloaded (minimum and maximum distances are given as short dashes at the extremes of the vertical dash); the mid-symbol circles are colour-coded by the number of stations downloaded (NSTA). For most of the events selected NSTA is about 35, for a few events NSTA is below 5, and for one event NSTA is greater than 40.

Manual picking

As shown in the previous section, we selected earthquakes in various distance ranges and of different sizes. This implies that the arrivals we may pick cover all those in the range of local/regional (e.g., Pg,Pn, Sg, Sn) and teleseismic phases (e.g., P, PP, S, SS, PKP, SKS etc.) and lots of care is required considering the high noise levels we may observe on OBS recordings. Figure 5 shows examples of unfiltered waveforms in different distance ranges (from a teleseismic hypocentral distance on the top left to a local distance on the bottom right) and the picks made. Even from the unfiltered waveforms shown in Figure 5 it is at times possible to identify primary seismic phases. However, in most cases different filter settings have been used depending on distance, noise level and earthquake size.

Figure 5: Examples of picked waveforms (raw unfiltered time series): a) station G21B ($\Delta=80.75^\circ$) for the 2013-02-06 01:12:26 $M_w=7.9$ Santa Cruz earthquake; b) station F01B ($\Delta=46.09^\circ$) for the 2012-09-05 14:42:07 $M_w=7.6$ Nicoya earthquake; c) station J28C ($\Delta=3.1^\circ$) for the 2014-03-13 19:11:34 $M_w=5.4$ Off Coast of Northern California earthquake; d) station G03D ($\Delta=0.64^\circ$) for the 2015-01-01 12:16:15 $M_w=5.4$ Off Coast of Northern California earthquake

Obviously, not all downloaded waveforms could be picked even after close inspection. Figure 6 shows a summary of the waveforms available for the selected earthquakes and the waveforms for which we obtained at least one pick.

Figure 6: number of stations for which we added at least one pick [NSTA(picked)] versus number of stations downloaded [NSTA(downloaded)]. The symbol shapes are dependent on magnitude and are colour-coded by the central distance of the 7D-OBS network to the earthquake. The dashed lines are shown for guidance to highlight the percentage of waveforms picked.

For the smaller earthquakes ($M_w < 6.0$) a smaller percentage of waveforms has been picked. For the larger events ($M_w > \sim 7.0$), the percentage of picked waveforms seems independent from the distance (i.e., if the event is large enough we could pick most of the waveforms even at large teleseismic distances). At the end of the internship period 6532 phases were picked. Table 1 summarizes the number of the most common phases picked.

Table 1: summary of the most recurrent picked phases

Phase	Count
S	2017
P	1753
SS	727
PP	687
PS	427
SSS	375
Pdif	201
PPP	132
pP	101
sP	88

We then integrated the 7D-OBS network picks together with the phase data in the ISC Bulletin to validate/discard the picks and to assess the effect of the 7D-OBS network after relocating the 99

selected earthquakes with the *iscloc* relocation program (Bondár and Storchak, 2011).

Relocation results

The picks of the 99 selected earthquakes were parsed into the ISC database and integrated with the data already available in the ISC Bulletin. At the time of running the relocations the last reviewed month in the ISC Bulletin was January 2014, and 39 out of 99 picked events fell into this reviewed period. This means that the relocations of the remaining 60 events should be considered as preliminary since the events in the unreviewed period have not yet been analysed by the ISC review team and also the data collection may not have been complete, particularly for events in 2015. Nevertheless, even for such events, the relocation with *iscloc* is a good way to evaluate the usefulness of the 7D-OBS picks. Indeed, the relocation procedures implemented in *iscloc* offer improved routines to re-identify the IASPEI standard phases (Storchak et al., 2013) with valid travel times using the *ak135* model (Kennett et al., 1995). More details about the location improvements obtained with *iscloc* can be found in Bondár and Storchak (2011). Here we only remark that if a phase is used in the ISC relocation then it becomes a time-defining phase (flag = T) with a certain time residual, whilst for non-defining phases *iscloc* attempts to re-identify the phase and calculate its time residual. After relocation with *iscloc*, 3418 (~52%) 7D-OBS picks were marked as time-defining, whilst 1693 (~26%) non-defining with time residuals ≤ 20 s and 754 (~11%) non-defining with time residuals > 20 s. For 667 (~10%) of the 7D-OBS picks *iscloc* was not able to compute a time residual (this happens mostly for PPP and SSS phases and other multiple surface reflections as *iscloc* does not compute a travel time for such phases). Table 2 summarizes the first 10 most common defining phases (and as re-identified by *iscloc*), and Figure 7 shows the time residual distribution of the 7D-OBS picks.

Table 2: summary of the most recurrent defining phases from the 7D-OBS picks. The “Re-identified phase” column lists the phase assigned by *iscloc*.

Picked phase	Re-identified phase	Count
P	P	705
S	S	489
P	Pn	432
S	Sn	387
S	Sb	220
PS	PS	218
SS	SS	176
PP	PP	171
Pdif	Pdif	112
PS	PnS	81

Figure 7: time residuals versus distance of the 7D-OBS picks of the 99 selected events after relocation with *iscloc*. The primary time-defining P and S waves are shown in red and blue, respectively, whilst other secondary defining picks are shown in yellow. The black dots indicate the non-defining picks (any phase). The histogram plot on the right shows the summary of the time residual distributions of the 7D-OBS picks.

To comprehend the overall effect of adding the 7D-OBS network to the ISC Bulletin data on our relocations, Figure 8 compares the number of defining stations (NDEFSTA) and the secondary azimuthal gap (SGAP, Bondár et al., 2004) before and after adding the 7D-OBS picks. Here, we compare only those earthquakes included in the reviewed ISC Bulletin (i.e., at the time of this report the last reviewed earthquake occurred in January 2014). This makes the comparisons more meaningful as they are obtained from the same location algorithm, and can be considered definitive as they have been reviewed by the ISC analysts. The largest and predominantly more distant earthquakes to the 7D-OBS network do not show significant improvements either in terms of NDEFSTA or SGAP. Note that the number of stations already available in the ISC Bulletin for these 39 events is much larger than the number of stations added with the 7D-OBS picks. For the smaller earthquakes that are typically closer to the 7D-OBS network we see a small improvement (i.e., reduction) in SGAP.

Figure 8: a) Comparison of number of defining stations (*NDEFSTA*) from ISC Bulletin data only and with the addition of the 7D-OBS picks; b) comparison of the secondary azimuthal gap (*SGAP*) obtained by relocation from ISC Bulletin data only and with the addition of the 7D-OBS picks. The symbol shapes are dependent on magnitude and are colour-coded by the central distance of the 7D-OBS network to the earthquake. Comparisons are only made for the 39 earthquakes relocated by the ISC at the time of this report (last reviewed earthquake in the ISC Bulletin occurred in January 2014).

Finally, Figure 9 shows the variation in epicenter location of the 39 earthquakes displayed in Figure 8 after adding the 7D-OBS network picks. Most of the epicenter location variations are within 15 km, with only 3 event epicenters varying by over 20 km. No obvious azimuthal bias seems to be introduced by the 7D-OBS network.

Figure 9: epicenter location variations after adding the 7D-OBS network for the 39 earthquakes displayed in Figure 8. Most of the variations are within 5 km (first circle), and only three above 20 km. No apparent bias appears to be introduced by the 7D-OBS picks in either direction.

Final remarks

The data coming from OBS stations is undoubtedly of primary importance in improving our understanding of Earth dynamics and the Earth's interior. For seismologists, in particular, OBS stations represent a unique opportunity to complement the data from on shore stations, especially in subduction zones where a significant proportion of earthquake activity occurs off shore. In this report we aimed at adding valuable seismic picks from the 7D-OBS experiment (http://www.fdsn.org/networks/detail/7D_2011/) into the ISC Bulletin. Such data would not be reported by any of the ~130 agencies currently contributing to the ISC Bulletin, and here we have shown that with limited time and human effort thousands of manual picks can be produced and can contribute to ISC relocations. The data we added from the 7D-OBS network will be available for free via the ISC website (www.isc.ac.uk) in the near future and, therefore, such OBS data will be available to the seismological community for years to come.

We encourage researchers processing data from temporary deployments to keep in mind the importance of storing valuable station data (possibly beyond what their own research requires) and to send parametric data to the ISC. This will allow us to improve the configuration network of the ISC locations and, in turn, improve specialised ISC datasets (e.g., ISC-EHB, GT and ISC-GEM) and offer an even denser dataset to ISC users.

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